

HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS. PART XXXII. NITRATION AND
BROMINATION OF 1-METHYL- AND 3-METHYL-
1:2:3:4-TETRAHYDRO-5-ACRIDONES

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7-Nitro-1-methyl-, 7:9-dinitro-1-methyl-, 7-nitro-3-methyl-, 9-nitro-3-methyl-, 7:9-dinitro-3-methyl-, 7-bromo-1-methyl-, 7:9-dibromo-1-methyl-, 7-bromo-3-methyl-, 9-bromo-3-methyl- and 7:9-dibromo-3-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridones have been prepared by direct nitration and bromination of 1-methyl- and 3-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridones. Their constitutions have been proved by their synthesis from suitably substituted nitro- and bromo-anthranilic acids and 1- and 3-methylcyclohexanones.

Bromination and nitration of 1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridones have been extensively studied. Thus, Desai and Buksh (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1939, 10A, 262), Huges and Lions (*J. Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1933, 71, 458), Huggill and Plant (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 784) have prepared 7-bromo-, while Huggill and Plant (*loc. cit.*) have also prepared 7:9-dibromo-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone. Perkin and Sedgwick (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2437), Travin and Magidson (*J. Gen. Chem U.S.S.R.*, 1937, 7, 842) and Huges and Lions (*loc. cit.*) have prepared 7-nitro-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone. The 8-nitro and 6-nitro derivatives were prepared by Perkin and Sedgwick (*loc. cit.*), while the 9-nitro derivative was prepared by Travin and Magidson (*loc. cit.*). As the nitration and bromination of 1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridones with a methyl substituent in the reduced benzene ring do not seem to have been studied, we have tried to prepare several nitro and bromo derivatives of 1-methyl- and 3-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridones.

1-Methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone on nitration gave 7-nitro-1-methyl and 7:9-dinitro-1-methyl derivatives. Similarly, 3-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone gave 7-nitro-3-methyl, 9-nitro-3-methyl and 7:9-dinitro-3-methyl derivatives. The constitutions of these compounds have been proved by their independent synthesis by condensing 5-nitro-, 3-nitro- and 3:5-dinitro-anthranilic acids with 1-methyl- and 3-methylcyclohexanones and comparing their melting and mixed melting points.

The bromination of 1-methyl- and 3-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridones gave mainly 7-bromo derivatives, but in the case of 3-methylacridone another isomer, 9-bromo derivative, was obtained. 7:9-Dibromo derivatives were obtained on dibromination in both the cases. The constitutions were proved by preparing the authentic specimens by condensing 5-bromo-, 3-bromo- and 3:5-dibromo-anthranilic acids with 1-methyl- and 3-methylcyclohexanones.

It is a general observation that an alkyl group exerts *ortho* and *para* directive influence, but as the methyl group is present in the reduced benzene ring, it is devoid of any influence and the nitration and bromination are mainly governed by the ring nitrogen atom.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

7-Nitro-1-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone.—1-Methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone (2.2 g.) was dissolved in H_2SO_4 (d 1.84, 15 c.c.). A mixture of HNO_3 (conc., 0.42 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 5.0 c.c.), cooled to -5° , was added to the cooled solution of the acridone with constant shaking. After keeping the flask in ice-box for 14 hours, the mixture was poured on crushed ice. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed, dried and then crystallised from toluene in bright yellow leaflets, m.p. 310° . (Found: N, 10.76. $C_{14}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.85%).

Synthesis of 1-Methyl-7-nitro-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone.—5-Nitroanthranilic acid (3.6 g.) and 1-methylcyclohexanone (2.3 g.) were heated at $130-40^\circ$ for 2 hours and then at $220-30^\circ$ for further one hour. The solid was extracted with a little alcohol to remove the impurities. The product was crystallised from toluene in yellow leaflets m.p. 310° , undepressed by admixture with the mononitro derivative.

7:9-Dinitro-1-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone.—1-Methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone was dinitrated in the same manner by taking the acridone (2.2 g.) and the nitrating mixture (0.84 c.c. of HNO_3 + 5 c.c. of H_2SO_4). The product was crystallised from alcohol in yellow leaflets, m.p. 315° . (Found: N, 14.1. $C_{14}H_{12}O_5N_2$ requires N, 14.33%).

Synthesis of 7:9-Dinitro-1-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone.—3:5-Dinitroanthranilic acid (1.5 g.) and 1-methylcyclohexanone (2.3 g.) were heated at $130-40^\circ$ for 2 hours and finally at $220-30^\circ$ to complete the reaction. The substance was crystallised from alcohol in yellow leaflets, m.p. 315° . The m.p. showed no depression when mixed with the dinitro derivative of the acridone.

7-Nitro-3-methyl- and 9-Nitro-3-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridones.—3-Methylacridone (2.2 g.) was nitrated by the nitrating mixture (15 c.c. of conc. HNO_3 + 5.0 c.c. of conc. H_2SO_4), and then kept in an ice-box for 12 hours. The solid, obtained by pouring the mixture into water, was filtered, washed and dried in a vacuum desiccator. It crystallised from alcohol in orange-yellow micro-crystals, m.p. 324° . This was proved to be the 7-nitro derivative by its mixed m.p. with the compound obtained from 5-nitroanthranilic acid and 3-methylcyclohexanone. (Found: N, 10.70. $C_{14}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.85%).

The yellowish mother-liquor on concentration and cooling deposited a solid in nodules, which after several crystallisations furnished pale yellow needles, m.p. 236° . This was proved to be the 9-nitro derivative by its mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen. (Found: N, 10.71. $C_{14}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.85%).

The 3-methylacridone was dinitrated by taking the acridone (2.6 g.) and the nitrating mixture (0.84 c.c. HNO_3 and 5.0 c.c. H_2SO_4) in the same manner as described above. The product was crystallised from alcohol in yellow plates, m.p. 271° which showed no depression when taken with the authentic specimen. (Found: N, 14.50. $C_{14}H_{12}O_5N_2$ requires N, 14.33%).

7-Bromo-1-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone.—1-Methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone (2.2 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (12 c.c.) and cooled to 5° ,

and a trace of iodine added. A 20% solution of bromine in acetic acid (5 c.c.) was added in one lot. The mixture was stirred for one hour at 10° and left in the ice-box for 24 hours. The light yellow precipitate, obtained by pouring the mixture in water, was filtered, dried and crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 292°. (Found: Br, 27.4. $C_{14}H_{11}ONBr$ requires Br, 27.40%).

Synthesis of 7-Bromo-1-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone.—A mixture of 5-bromoanthranilic acid (2.16 g.) and 1-methylcyclohexanone (1.12 g.) was heated at 180° for 1 hour and then at 230-40° for 45 minutes. The solid was crystallised from alcohol in yellowish needles, m.p. 291-92°, and showed no depression when taken with the monobromo derivative of the acridone.

7:9-Dibromo-1-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone.—The acridone (2.13 g.) was dibrominated by using a 20% bromine solution in glacial acetic acid (9.6 c.c.) as above. The compound crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow leaflets, m.p. 215°. (Found: Br, 42.92. $C_{14}H_{11}ONBr_2$ requires Br, 43.12%).

Synthesis of 7:9-Dibromo-1-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone.—A mixture of 3:5-dibromoanthranilic acid (2.63 g.) and 1-methylcyclohexanone (1.12 g.) was heated as above and the compound was obtained as yellowish leaflets, m.p. 215°. The m.p. was undepressed when taken with the dibromo derivative of the acridone.

7-Bromo-3-methyl- and 9-Bromo-3-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone.—To a solution of 3-methylacridone (4.26 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) a trace of iodine was added, followed by a 20% bromine solution (5.0 c.c.), as in the case of 1-methyl analogue. On pouring the mixture into water, a yellowish substance settled down which was filtered, washed with water and dried. When crystallised from alcohol (90%), colorless needles were obtained, m.p. 321°. This compound was proved to be the 7-bromo derivative by its mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen. (Found: Br, 27.35. $C_{14}H_{11}ONBr$ requires Br, 27.40%).

The mother-liquor on evaporation gave an amorphous mass which on crystallisation from a mixture of ethyl and methyl alcohols (2:1) gave shining prismatic needles, m.p. 317°, depressed to 301° by the 7-bromo derivative. (Found: Br, 27.35. $C_{14}H_{11}ONBr$ requires Br, 27.40%).

The m.p.s of the bromo derivatives were undepressed when taken with the authentic specimens.

7:9-Dibromo 3-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone.—7-Bromo-3-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone (2.9 g.) was brominated by the 20% bromine solution (5 c.c.) at 50°. The solid obtained on pouring the mixture into water was filtered, washed and dried. It crystallised from alcohol in orange-yellow plates, m.p. 151°. It showed no depression in m.p. when taken with the authentic specimen. (Found: Br, 43.30. $C_{14}H_{11}ONBr_2$ requires Br, 43.12%).

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